

Embiids (Insecta: Embioptera) in the collections of the National Museum of Natural History (Sofia), identified by E.S. Ross

Petar BERON

Abstract: A collection of Embioptera, or Embiidina (P. Beron leg.) was sent to Dr Ross (California), identified and returned with some taxa indicated as “new”, but this material has not been published. Here is a list of the collection (16 sp. from 10 genera and two families) from 17 countries (Bulgaria, Greece (incl. Rhodes, Kassos, Crete, Samotraki), Libya, Nigeria, Cameroon, Senegal, Zimbabwe, Tunisia, France (Corsica), Italy (Sardinia), India, Afghanistan, Mozambique, Papua New Guinea, Cuba, Mexico, USA).

Key words: Embiidina, list, Museum Sofia

During my travels in many countries, I collected some Embiidina and have sent them to Dr E.S. Ross in California. He returned the material identified, indicating some specimens as new taxa, but they have not been published (in litt.). I think that it would be interesting to publish these identifications, for information to the specialists about the availability of this group in the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia.

The collection consists of 16 species of 10 genera and the families Embiidae and Oligotomidae. They originate from 17 countries: Bulgaria, Greece (incl. Rhodes, Kassos, Crete, Samotraki), Libya, Nigeria, Cameroon, Senegal, Zimbabwe, Tunisia, France (Corsica), Italy (Sardinia), India, Afghanistan, Mozambique, Papua New Guinea, Cuba, Mexico, USA.

Order Embioptera (Embiidina)

Fam. Embiidae

Berlandembia berlandi (Navás, 1922)

Nigeria, Plateau State, Pai River Game Reserve, Sabon Gida Guard Post, 9.04.1978, light

Nigeria, idem, 10.04.1978

Nigeria, idem, 18.04.1978

Nigeria, Plateau State, Wase Rock Game Res., 1.06.1978

Cleomia guareschi Stefani, 1953

Tunisia, Tabarka, 10.05.1971, E.S. Ross leg. et det. (donation)

Embia josensis Ross (topotype)

Embia ramburi Rimsky-Korsakow, 1905

Corsica, Caporalino, 17.10.1967 (Ny)

Tunisia, 10 km from Maktar, Sept. 1970, E.S.

Ross leg. et det. (donation)

Embia n.sp. MS

Nigeria, Plateau State, Wase Rock Game Res., 1.06.1978

Embia sp. (f, Ny, difficult to identify)

Sardinia, Distr. Sassari, Laerru, 17.10.1980

Sardinia, Bonorva, 16.10.1980

Sardinia, Cagliari

Cameroon, 70 km E Nanga Eboko, 2.01.1977

(♀♀, ny)

Zimbabwe, Great Zimbabwe Ruins, 20.08.1983

Leptembia furcata Ross, n.sp. MS

Nigeria, Plateau State, Jos Wildlife Park, 1350 m, 24.03.1978

Nigeria, idem, 27.03.1978

Nigeria, idem, 12.04.1977

Leptembia protruda Ross, n.sp. MS

Nigeria, Plateau State, Pai River Game Reserve, Sabon Gida Guard Post, 9.04.1978

Nigeria, idem, 16.04.1977

Leptembia sp. (♀, ny.)

Nigeria, Plateau State, Wase Rock Game Reserve, 4.09.1978

Leptembia sp. (♂, ny.)

- Nigeria, Pandam Wildlife Park, 14.02.1977
Parembia valida (Hagen, 1885)
 India, Delhi, 24.06.1981
Parembia persica (McLachlan, 1877)
 Afghanistan, Kabul, 2-19.06.1986, 1800 m
Plesioembia gen., n., sp. n., MS
 Nigeria, Plateau State, Jos, July 1978
 Nigeria, Plateau State, Jos, 1350 m, 25.05.1978
 (adult ♀♀)
 Fam. **Oligotomidae**
Aposthonia minuscula (Enderlein, 1912)
 Mozambique, Cabo Delgado Prov., Mecufi, 6 –
 15.07.1983
Aposthonia n.sp.? “nr. *davisi* - Ross, in litt.”
 Papua New Guinea, Telefomin, West Sepik
 Prov., 1660 m, 22.07.1975
Haploembia solieri (Rambur, 1842)
 Bulgaria, Rhodopes, Mezek, 29.03.1986
 Greece, Crete, Psiloritis, 1600-2000 m,
 11.05.1984
 Greece, Crete, Psiloritis, nr. Zoniana, 700-900
 m, 13.05.1984
 Greece, Distr. Evros, Avas Village, 17.05.1987
 Greece, Samotraki, Chora Village, 20.05.1984
 Greece, Rhodes, Laerma, 1.05.1984 (juv. ♀)
 Corsica, Cargèse, Orchino Peninsula, 10 m alt.,
 12.11.1967
 Sardinia, Capo Caccia, nr. Alghero, 18.10.1980
 USA, California, Redwood City, matured,
 1.06.1969, E.S. Ross leg. et det., donation
Haploembia megacephala Krauss, 1911
 Greece, Kassos, Aghia Marina, 6.05.1984
 Greece, Rhodes, Archangelos Village,
 2.05.1987
Oligotoma humberiana (Saussure, 1896)
 Mozambique, Cabo Delgado Prov., Mecufi, 28
 -31.07.1983
 Mozambique, idem, 28-31.07.1983
 Mozambique, Catuane Prov., Maputu,
 24.06.1983
 Tanzania, Moshi, 800 m, 7.09.1983
Oligotoma saundersii (Westwood, 1837)
 Cuba, Santiago de Cuba, 24.02.1982
 Cuba, idem, 10.03.1982
 Nigeria, Plateau State, Jos, 1300 m, February 1978
 Senegal, Ile de Gorée, 14.08.1977
 Mozambique, Cabo Delgado Prov., Mecufi, 6 –
 15.07.1983
 Papua New Guinea, New Britain, Rabaul,
 18.11.1975, under bark
 Many ♀♀ and nymphes of several species
 Nigeria, Plateau State, Jos, 12-30. Sept. 1976
Non-identified material:
 Libya, Sabratha, 0-20 m, 19.04.1998, P. Beron leg.
 Mexico, Ciudad Victoria, Tamaulipas,
 26.01.1982, Gen., sp. (♂, ny, seen by Dr Ross)

References

- MILLER K.B., HAYASHI C., WHITING M.F., GAVIN J., SVENSON N., EDGERLY J. 2012. The phylogeny and classification of Embioptera (Insecta). – *Systematic Entomology*, **37**: 550–570.
- ROSS E.S. 2003. EMBIA. Contribution to the Biosystematics of the Insect Order Embiidina. Part 5. A Review of the Family Anisembiidae with descriptions of new taxa. – *Occasional Papers of the Californian Academy of Sciences*, **154**: 1-123.

Author's address:

Received: 10.11.2015

Petar Beron, National Museum of Natural History – BAS, Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd. 1, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

Ембии (Insecta: Embioptera) в колекциите на Националния природонаучен музей (София)

Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

В колекциите на НПМ (София) има значителна серия от ембии (16 вида от 10 рода и две семейства), между които нови за науката видове и род от Афганистан, България, Гърция, Зимбабве, Индия, Камерун, Корсика, Куба, Ливан, Мексико, Мозамбик, Нигерия, Папуа Нова Гвинея, Сардиния, Сенегал, Танзания, САЩ. Материалът е събран от П. Берон и е определен частично от Dr Edward S. Ross от Калифорнийската академия на науките (Сан Франциско). По-късно е постъпил и материал от Либия, който не е определен.